

EMPLOYMENT AND LABOR RESOURCES OF URBAN AND RURAL POPULATION OF KASHKADARYA REGION IN THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE.

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Key words: Kashkadarya region, population of the region, urban population, rural population, number of women, number of men, social sphere, infrastructure, working population, population employed in the national economy, labor department, monetary income of the population, labor resources.

Abstract: In this article, the issue of population employment in the cities and villages of the Kashkadarya region during the years of independence is analyzed over the years. Comparisons and comparisons with other regions and previous years are made and specific conclusions are drawn.

President Sh. Speaking, Mirziyoev said, "Kashkadarya region takes a leading place in the development of our country. It is not easy to be the leader of Kashkadarya, a region with more than 3.5 million inhabitants. The land of Kashkadarya is rich, the soil is fertile, and the people are hardworking. It's only necessary to unite them, work together and work honestly»[1]. The head of state noted that this year, an additional 360 billion soums will be allocated from the republic's budget to improve the social sphere and infrastructure in Kashkadarya. Also, 100 million dollars of preferential funds will be directed from the funds of international financial institutions. Today, 350,000 people are in need of work, and it is important to attract them to entrepreneurship, handicrafts, and homemaking based on the new neighborhood system [4:1492-1495]. was recorded.

The population of the province in 1999 was 2166.3 thousand people, of which 1061.5 thousand were men and 1104.8 thousand were women. Out of that, the urban population was 553.1 thousand people, 265.5 thousand men, 287.6 thousand women, 1613.2 thousand rural residents, 790.4 thousand men, 822.8 thousand women. In 2000, there were 2212.7 thousand people, of which 1084.2 thousand were men and 1128.5 thousand were women. Out of that, the urban population was 561,700 people, 269,600 men, 292,100 women, 1651,000 rural people, 807,300 men, 843,700 women. In 2001, there were 2294.7 thousand people, of which 1104.3 thousand were men and 1149.4 thousand were women. Out of that, the urban population was 563,700 people, 270,600 men, 293,100 women, 1690,000 rural people, 828,100 men, 861,900 women. In 2002, the population was 2294.7 thousand people, of which 1148.9 thousand men and 1145.8 thousand women. Out of that, the urban population was 572,500, men 286,900, women 285,600, rural population 1722,200, men 862,000, women 860,200.

In Kashkadarya region, the number of working-age population in 1999 was 982.2 thousand people, in 2000 it was 999.5 thousand people, in 2001 it was 1045.5 thousand people, in 2002, 2003 it was 1102.3 thousand people. The population employed in the national economy was 753.1 thousand people in 1999, 725.0 thousand people in 2000, 736.2 thousand people in 2001, 750.7 thousand people in 2002, and 770.5 thousand people in 2003. The number of unemployed persons registered in labor offices was 1489 people in 1999, 1900 people in 2000, 2098 people in 2001, 2002 1782 people. In 2003, there were 1616 people. As of 1999, there were 753,100 people employed in the economy in the province, of which 131,400 people worked in state enterprises

and organizations, and 621,700 people in non-governmental organizations. In 2000, it employed 725,000 people, including 126,200 people in state enterprises and organizations, and 598,800 people in non-state organizations [2].

In 1999, the total working age population of the region was 928.3 thousand people, and in 2002 it was 1 million 115.8 thousand people. From this, in 1999, the working age population was as follows in the districts. 108.4 thousand people in Shahrisabz district, 105.8 thousand people in Karshi city, 93.9 people in Chirakchi district, 87.5 thousand people in Yakkabog district, 85.1 thousand people in Qamashi district, 81.9 thousand people in Koson district, 73 in Karshi district ,2 thousand people, Kitab district 69,5 thousand people, Guzor [5:135-138] district 55,4 thousand people, Kasbi [6:1-6] district 49,2 thousand people, Mirishkor district 35,3 thousand people , 33.8 thousand people in Nishan district, 28.9 thousand people in Dehkanabad district, 20.4 thousand people in Mubarak district.

By 2002, this indicator was 131.5 thousand people in Shahrisabz district, 122.0 people in Chiraqi district, 110.6 thousand people in Karshi city, 93.5 thousand people in Kitab district, 88.5 thousand people in Yakkabog district, 87.0 people in Qamashi district. thousand people, 85.1 thousand people in Koson district, 85.1 thousand people in Karshi district, 65.2 thousand people in Guzor [9:128-131] district, 64.1 thousand people in Kasbi [8:96-100] district, Nishan District 46.5 thousand people, Dehkanabad district 45.6 thousand people, Mirishkor district 43.1 thousand people, Mubarak district 38.6 thousand people.

In 1999, the monetary income of the population amounted to 106,031 million soums, and the expenses amounted to 81,142 million soums. Of this, per capita income is 49.4 soums, and expenses It was 37.8 soums.

In 2002, the monetary income of the population was 334,564.0 million soums, and the expenses were 295,282.9 million soums. From this, per capita income was 176.1 soums, and expenses were 129.5 soums[2].

In 1999, the salary of employees working in economic sectors amounted to 7935.7 thousand soums, of which the salary of employees working in financial and state insurance institutions was 7957.5 thousand soums, the salary of employees in the industrial sector was 8181.4 thousand soums, the salary of employees in the field of science and scientific service was 4352 0,000 soums, wages of construction workers 7,375,100 soums, wages of transport workers 5,083,200 soums, management office workers 7,120,000 soums, communication workers 6,057,400 soums, housing, communal services, household service workers salary 6937.5 thousand soums, agriculture and forestry workers salary 4319.0 thousand soums, trade and general catering workers salary 6377.2 thousand soums, education workers salary 6511.0 thousand soums, culture and the salary of art workers was 5,545,000 soums, and the salary of health, physical education, and social welfare workers was 5,691,000 soums.

These figures show that by 2002, the salary of employees working in economic sectors amounted to 15,485.5 thousand soums, of which the salary of employees working in financial and state insurance institutions was 32,365,0 thousand soums, the salary of employees in the industrial sector was 41,215,0 thousand soums, science and scientific service [7:121-123] the salary of employees in the field is 14660.0 thousand soums, the salary of employees in the construction sector is 26315.0 thousand soums, the salary of employees in the field of transport is 20644.6 thousand soums, the employees of management offices are 27060.0 thousand soums, the communication employees are 28197, 4

1,000 soums, housing, communal services, household service workers salary 13,580.0 thousand soums, agriculture and forestry workers 8,176.2 thousand soums, trade and catering workers 16,821.6 thousand soums, education employees' salary was 14086.0 thousand soums, culture and art employees' salary was 12448.0 thousand soums, healthcare, physical education, social welfare employees' salary was 15124.0 thousand soums.

The number of working population in 2004 was 1 million 195.8 thousand people, in 2006 it was 1295.8 thousand people. The number of children of preschool age (under 6 years) was 435.8 thousand in 2004 and 443.7 thousand in 2006 [2].

The number of people employed in the economy was 796,400 in 2004, 821,700 in 2005, and 850,000 in 2006. The number of unemployed people registered in the Labor Department was 2,271 in 2004, 2,532 in 2005, and 2,781 in 2006.

Labor resources of the region in 2004 were 1 million 199.6 thousand people, by 2006 it was 1 million 301.4 thousand people. In 2004, the number of working-age population in the districts was 141,000 in Shahrisabz district, 131,000 in Chirakchi district, 119,700 in Karshi city, 101,300 in Koson district, 99,000 in Kitab district, 95,100 in Yakkabog district. thousand, 93.1 thousand in Qamashi district, 92.7 thousand in Karshi district, 70.4 thousand in Guzor district, 69.0 thousand in Kasbi district, 50.2 thousand in Nishan district, 49.2 thousand in Dehkhanaabad district, 46.3 thousand in Mirishkor district, in the Mubarak district, there were 41.6 thousand people.

By 2006, this indicator was 1 million 301.4 thousand people. Of this, 151,000 people live in Shahrisabz district, 141,900 people in Chiraqi district, 128,900 people in Karshi city, 108,600 people in Koson district, 107,100 people in Kitab district, 106,500 people in Yakkabog district, 101 thousand in Qamashi district, 100.9 thousand in Karshi district, 76.4 thousand in Guzor district, 75.0 thousand in Kasbi district, 54.5 thousand in Nishan district, 53.7 thousand in Dehkhanaabad district, 50.5 thousand in Mirishkor district, 45 in Mubarak district made up 4,000 people.

In 2004, 796,400 people were employed in the economy [10:396-400], of which 177,900 were employed in state enterprises and organizations, 618,500 people were employed in non-state enterprises and organizations. By 2006, 850,000 people worked in economic sectors, 182,000 people worked in state enterprises and organizations, and 668,000 people worked in non-state enterprises and organizations.

The population of Kashkadarya region in 2011 was 2 million 777.8 people, of which 1390.8 thousand men and 1387.0 thousand women. The population of the city is 1203.9, men are 602.7 thousand, women are 601.2 thousand, rural population is 1573.9 thousand, of which men are 788.1 thousand and women are 785.8 thousand.

In 2014, the population of the region was 2960.6 thousand people, of which 1487.7 thousand men and 1472.9 thousand women. The population of the city is 1275.2, men are 641.4 thousand, women are 633.8 thousand, rural population is 1685.4 thousand, of which men are 846.3 thousand and women are 839.1 thousand.

In 2011, the working population was 1,564,1 people, and in 2014, it was 1,690,6 thousand people. The population employed in the economy was 1003.7 thousand people, in 2014 it was 1108.5 thousand people.

According to preliminary data, the number of cocktail resources in the Kura region for the months of January-December 2017 was 1784.6 thousand people on average, or 57.2% of the total population.

As part of labor resources, the number of economically active population is 1296.6 thousand people of the total labor resources (72.6%), as well as the number of economically inactive population (27.3%). There were 488,000 people

The share of the economically active population in the total population was 41.6%.

The largest number of economically [11:73-76] active population was observed in Chirakchi (156.7 thousand people) and Shakhrisabz (142.1 thousand people) districts.

The lowest indicators of the number of economically active population correspond to the districts of Mubarak (30.4 thousand people) and Mirishkor (49.9 thousand people) came. According to preliminary data, the number of people employed in the economy for the period of January-December 2017 amounted to 1218.0 thousand people, which increased by 9.8% compared to 2016.

The main part of the employed population is rural, forest and fisheries (28.1%), industry (8.4%), trade (10.3%), education (8.3%) and construction (13.9%) contributed.

In January-December 2017, the employment rate of the economically active population (the ratio of economically active population to the number of economically active population) was 93.9%. The share of total jobs in the non-state sector reached 84.3%, and in the same period of 2016 it was 83.9%[2].

The number of unemployed people determined based on the method of counting the unemployed population in need of employment approved by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 106 of May 24, 2007 [12:26-28] was 98,100 people in January-December 2017 and the rate of unemployment in relation to the number of economically active population was equal to 7.6%.

The average monthly nominal salary in December 2017 amounted to 1826.3 thousand soums and increased by 7.0% compared to December 2016. The average monthly nominal salary for the months of January-December 2017 amounted to 1342.9 thousand soums and increased by 9.0% compared to the corresponding period of 2016.

In the 3rd quarter of 2021, the average monthly salary in Kashkadarya region is 2317271 soums, by sectors, including 3610188 soums in industry, 2758462 soums in construction, 2203550 soums in trade, transportation and storage 3257075 soums, living and dining 1450917 soums, information and communication 302 0521 soums, financial and insurance activities amounted to 6236468 soums, education 1975692 soums, health care 1710814 soums, art 2100653 soums, other areas 2378393 soums[3]. So, effective work is being done in Kashkadarya region to improve the social sphere and infrastructure.

Literature

1. Қарши шаҳрида 2018 йил 22 апрель куни халқ депутатлари Қашқадарё вилояти Кенгашининг навбатдан ташқари сессиясида Президент Ш.Мирзиёев нутқи.
2. Қашқадарё вилоятининг 1999-2019 йилларда вилоят паспорти маълумотлари.
3. Қашқадарё вилояти статистика бошқармаси маълумотлари.
4. Hasanov, A. (2020). Kesh-Shakhrisabz oasis in the middle ages. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 29(5), 1492-1495.
5. Khudaykulovich, E. A. (2022). Guzar's ethymology in Historical Sources. *International Journal of Development and Public Policy*, 2(3), 135-138.
6. Muminovich, H. A. (2022). TERRITORIAL AND GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION OF THE CITIES OF THE TERMIZ OASIS IN THE EARLY MIDDLE AGES. *Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development*, 6, 1-6.

7. Karimov, B. (2021). Historical Geography of Yakkabog District. *International Journal of Development and Public Policy*, 1(4), 121-123.
8. Khasanov, A. M. (2021). Historical and Geographical Regions of Chaghaniyan. *International Journal of Development and Public Policy*, 1(4), 96-100
9. Xudaykulovich, E. A. (2022). Handicraft and Trade in Guzar District. *International Journal of Development and Public Policy*, 1(8), 128-131.
10. Hasanov, A. (2023). ABUL MUIN AN-NASAFI–THE PROMOTER OF TEACHING OF" MOTURIDIYA". *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(2), 396-400
11. Muminov, U. (2021). Historical Gates of Karshi. *International Journal of Development and Public Policy*, 1(6), 73-76.
12. Matluba, R. (2022). THE ROLE OF THE HISTORICAL MONUMENTS OF THE KASHKADARYA OASIS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. *Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development*, 6, 26-28.

